

Calculating the strength of the Plastic pump In counteracting the Deep export of Oceanic carbon (CUPIDO)

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Introduction

Plastic pollution is now considered among the planetary boundary threats, with production and pathways of plastic into marine ecosystems increasing exponentially since the 1970's. Today, the global abundance of plastic afloat in the world's oceans is estimated to be between 82 – 358 trillion plastic particles, weighing 1.1 – 7.9 million tonnes. The amount of plastic entering our oceans is increasing with global implications for the health of our planet (Borrelle et al., 2020). As this plastic debris degrades in the ocean, fragmentation will shift particle size from large plastics to smaller microplastics, even in the absence of any new inputs (Andrady, 2017). Thus, the problem of microplastic pollution will only increase in future years. However, the ways in which microplastics are transported to the deep ocean are still largely unknown (Porter et al., 2020). This limits our ability to determine the impacts of plastic debris on the ocean ecosystem. Microplastic debris interact with highly dynamic communities of zooplankton. These small organisms, which are at the base of marine food chains, ingest microplastics and repackage them into faecal pellets which may become deposited deep in the ocean over the cycle of diel vertical migration (Cole et al., 2016). Microplastics may also become incorporated into zooplankton body tissue which, at the end of life, will sink as part of the carcass (Wieczorek et al., 2019).

CUPIDO team have measured how the characteristics of plastics alter as a function of exposure to the marine environment, the vertical distribution and export of plastic over daily and seasonal timescales, and the role of zooplankton as vectors of plastics through the water column (Manno et al., 2022). This wealth of novel data will be analysed and modelled to predict: (i) the accumulation of plastics in specific water layers through the water column and (ii) how the flux of plastics and C alters over an annual cycle in regions of high and low plastic debris input.

Overall, CUPIDO addresses the hypothesis that zooplankton and food-web-associated processes play a major role in promoting the sinking of plastic through the water column. These mechanisms will decrease the ability of the marine ecosystem to transfer C from the surface to the deep ocean.

Figure: (left) OPIC, Ocean Plastic In-situ Incubator Chambers, first deployment in the Mediterranean Sea; right: Cruise team on the DALLAPORTA research vessel including some members of the CUPIDO team.

Objectives

The main objective of CUPIDO is to investigate the interaction of marine ecosystem, plastic pollution and carbon cycle and understand how this interaction is impacting the climate change.

CUPIDO measure the microplastic export in two contrasting environments. The first site is in the Southern Ocean. The second site is in the Mediterranean Sea. The contrasting conditions of the two selected regions (relatively pristine vs. highly polluted) allow for an analysis of the impact of microplastic on the ocean's ability to export and sequester C at low and high plastic input regimes. The access to the platform ASOS (Adriatic Sea Observation System) was then strategically fundamental to achieve CUPIDO objectives.

CUPIDO has 4 major objectives:

- *OB.1 Install an ocean array to determine in situ temporal variability in oceanic plastic particle characteristics.*
- *OB.2 Measure the flux of plastics to different ocean depths and how this varies seasonally*

- *OB.3 Identify and quantify the mechanisms by which zooplankton facilitate the penetration of plastic in the ocean.*
- *OB.4 Build up an ecological model (using outcomes of OB1-3) to assess the interaction between carbon and microplastic export*

Methodology

The in-situ incubator chambers (OPIC) were deployed on mooring FF on spring 2022 and recovered on autumn 2023 during two research cruises on board of DellaPorta and Gaia Blu.

OPIC is a unique device, built in-house to our own design to evaluate how oceanic plastics alter over long time scales through incubating pre-selected meso- and microplastics in in-situ conditions. OPIC has in-built carousels that expose the pre-selected plastic particles for different periods of time (from months to a year) over the duration of deployment. The cumulative exposure time of plastic samples (pristine and aged polymers) in the natural environment allowed rates of degradation to be quantified. Pathways for degradation in terms of physical- (fragmentation, agglomeration) and chemical (polymer molecular structure) characteristics of plastic in the natural marine environment have been also investigated.

At each research cruises a Floating Trap was deployed for 24h. Floating trap was equipped with open-close mechanisms to estimate the penetration of plastic and carbon concentration through the first 200m to a high degree of vertical resolution (i.e. one floating unit each 40 m). *This trap, specially designed in-house, represents the first plastic free trap of its kind.*

Back to British Antarctic Survey all the samples have been analysed using a combination of technique including Infrared spectrum measurement (FTIR) and Scanning electron microscopy analysis for the characterise and quantify of microplastic while carbon was measured by combustion in an elemental analyzer (CHN).

Results

Plastic and Carbon flux interaction

Preliminary results show that microplastic fluxes were relatively high reaching a maximum of 814 pieces $\text{m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$ at 100m demonstrating that this pollution extends below the surface layer. Plastics <1 mm dominated the flux (87%). In terms of polymeric composition, polyvinyl chloride was most common followed by Polyamide. at both 50 and 100 meters and polyester at 150 metres. We only found one polymer less dense than seawater in our samples, polypropylene at 100 and 150 meters. Overall, our findings reveal that the Adriatic Sea hosts exceptionally high vertical fluxes of microplastics, with important implications for both microplastic transport and carbon cycling. These results will be compared with carbon flux collected from the samples in order to calculate the variability of microplastic: carbon ratio along the water column.

Plastic degradation over the season

This study reveals the natural weathering behaviour of plastic polymers in the marine environment using a novel equipment. The findings of this study demonstrate that the extent of weathering varied by time and plastic polymer type as function of environmental conditions (chemical (i.e. change in physical, chemical and biological factors)). Overall, we found that degradation over the year affects all the pre-selected plastic fragments in terms of change in density/porosity and (in turn) sinking potential. The degradation of plastics in the ocean is a multifaceted process that poses significant environmental challenges. Understanding the mechanisms and factors influencing this degradation is essential for developing effective strategies to mitigate the impact of plastic pollution on marine ecosystems.

Conclusions and Future work

The project has combined what is traditionally seen as ocean biogeochemistry with the emerging field of marine plastic pollution. The CUPIDO project reveals that microplastics threaten not only marine life but also the ocean's role in stabilising climate. By interfering with zooplankton, plastics may slow the transport of carbon to the deep sea, weakening a key natural carbon sink.

By observing the behaviour of microplastic below the sea surface, prior to eventual deposition on the seabed, we improve our understanding of microplastic pathways in the ocean. Such insights are essential for refining biogeochemical models that incorporate this newly emerging carbon export pathway, which is particularly timely given the scale of increasing microplastic pollution.

We are planning the publication of three peer review papers, furthermore data acquired will support our modelling effort aims to simulate the interaction between microplastics and carbon export in the ocean. The next step for CUPIDO is to build on these findings by applying again to the EMSO ERIC programme. Integrating CUPIDO's tools and data within EMSO's long-term observatories will allow us to scale up monitoring of plastics and their impact on the carbon cycle

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